

Forecasting Models for Maintenance Work Load With Seasonal Components

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SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the results of applying time series forecasting techniques to the forecasting of maintenance work load. In particular, this paper discusses several models developed to forecast the electronics maintenance work load for a weather forecasting system located in Alaska. The maintenance work load for this system typically increases during the winter season. This is mostly due to the system's remote geographic locations and the additional travel time required to reach these locations during the harsh Alaskan winter. Several models were developed and evaluated on the basis of their data fit and forecasting accuracy of seasonal and non-seasonal electronics maintenance work load.

In the first part of the analysis, a regression model that uses a serial autocorrelated error correction procedure was developed to model the non-seasonal components of the work load. Seasonal work load components were modeled using seasonal and cyclical indicator variables. The cyclical indicator variables were effective in modeling this system's seasonal work load behavior. A model that uses a combination of seasonal and cyclical indicator variables was also effective in this respect.

In the second part of the analysis, seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) techniques were used to model and forecast maintenance work load. A brief description of these forecasting methods and the procedures used to identify an optimal work load forecasting model are provided. Two seasonal ARIMA models were developed: The first model used only maintenance predictor variables; the second model used a combination of maintenance predictor variables and cyclical indicator variables.

All of the models were evaluated on the basis of their goodness-of-fit and forecasting accuracy. A seasonal ARIMA model that uses a combination of maintenance predictor variables and cyclical indicator variables had the best goodness-of-fit and provided the most accurate maintenance work load forecast. Cyclical indicator variables were found to be extremely effective in modeling the seasonal behavior of the maintenance work load in both the causal and stochastic models.

1. INTRODUCTION

The NOAA National Weather Service (NWS) owns and maintains thousands of weather forecasting systems and

equipment. Examples of such systems include Doppler weather radars and weather radio transmitters. These systems are maintained by several hundred electronics maintenance technicians stationed at local weather forecast offices throughout the United States. Much of the equipment associated with these systems is installed at remote locations. Thus, travel time to and from these equipment locations is often a major component of their overall maintenance work load.

The maintenance travel work load is especially high during the winter for remote NWS systems located in Alaska. Extreme weather conditions significantly increase maintenance travel times in Alaska during winter. Maintenance travel that is routinely completed within a day or two frequently takes several days to complete during winter. In this paper, the maintenance work load for a weather forecasting system located in Alaska was modeled and forecasted using a combination of seasonal and non-seasonal maintenance work load predictor variables.

Maintenance-related information is reported through a centralized maintenance data collection system by the technician assigned the maintenance action. Maintenance information is reported and categorized as follows: routine/preventive, non-routine/corrective, travel, and miscellaneous maintenance. Routine/preventive maintenance tasks are scheduled maintenance actions performed on equipment to ensure that it continues to operate properly and to minimize the probability of failure. Non-routine/corrective maintenance pertains to remedial actions taken to correct equipment failures and restore equipment to its proper operational condition. Travel is the total travel time expended on a maintenance action. Miscellaneous maintenance includes maintenance time expended on maintenance-related actions such as maintenance training, first-line maintenance supervision, and tasks related to commissioning and decommissioning of systems and equipment.

Historically, corrective maintenance and travel time variables have had relatively high variances. On the other hand, the difference in actual routine and miscellaneous work loads from what is projected by maintenance managers for a given month has tended to be small. This difference is mostly due to differences in the skill and proficiency of the technicians performing the maintenance. Historical work load averages for routine maintenance tasks are usually available.

The routine time (*rt*) and miscellaneous time (*misc*) maintenance variables will be used as independent maintenance work load predictors of the maintenance work load (*wl*), the dependent variable to be forecasted. This work load is

measured in staff-years (S-Y). The maintenance work load derivation is an agency-specific one that is calculated by taking into account the total number of available technician hours per year, the total reported maintenance hours, technicians' vacation and sick hours, and the estimated number of productive maintenance hours per technician per year.

The work load time series used in this paper consists of 90 monthly observations. The last five observations were removed from the series for later testing and validation of the models' forecasting accuracy. The automated maintenance data collection system from which the data was obtained is about eight years old. Prior to the establishment of this data collection system, maintenance data was submitted on paper and it is considered to be significantly less reliable than data collected through the current automated system.

2. NOTATION LIST

ACF	Autocorrelation Function
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
β	Regressor Coefficient Value
MISC	Miscellaneous Maintenance in Hours
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
ρ	Cochrane-Orcutt Autoregression Coefficient
PACF	Partial Autocorrelation Function
R^2	Coefficient of Determination
RT	Routine/Preventive Maintenance in Hours
S_t	Seasonal/Cyclical Component at Time t
σ^2	Error Variance
SBC	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion
SEB	Standard Error in Regressor Coefficient
SSE	Sum of the Squares of Error
WL	Maintenance Work Load in Staff-years

3. EXPLORING THE MAINTENANCE WORK LOAD

The maintenance work load time series is shown in Figure 1. It consists of 90 monthly observations.

Figure 1

The time series Boxplot is shown in Figure 2. The Boxplot reveals that the median and interquartile range of the winter season maintenance work load are larger than those of the other seasons.

Figure 2

The Student t-test ratio for winter work load depicting its statistical significance is shown in Table 1. The winter maintenance work load is statistically significant at about the 95% confidence level. The calendar months work load was not statistically significant as none of the months had a t-test ratio corresponding to a 90% or higher confidence level using only months as maintenance work load predictor variables in an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) multiple regression model.

Table 1

Predictor	T- Ratio	Sig. T
Fall	0.82	0.4122
Winter	1.96	0.0536
Spring	0.09	0.9261
Constant	5.89	0.0000

Dependent variable: Work Load

4. ANALYSIS

4.1 Causal Models

The maintenance work load was fitted, modeled, and forecasted using an autoregression procedure with serial autocorrelation error correction. The non-seasonal work load components were modeled using an OLS regression model consisting of the lagged work load, routine time, miscellaneous time, and time (trend) as work load predictor variables. (The lagged work load was only initially included in the models and then removed due to its statistical insignificance as determined during the backward regression processes to reach the 95% confidence level for the predictor variables.) The seasonal component of work load was modeled using seasonal

and cyclical indicator variables. The OLS methods assume linearity, normality, independence, and constant variance. Linear relationships between the work load (dependent variable) and each of routine time (*rt*) and miscellaneous time (*misc*) (independent variables) were investigated graphically using scatterplot diagrams. Both relationships were found to be strongly linear as the points clustered around a straight line. All the models presented in this paper were tested for white noise residuals to satisfy the remaining OLS assumptions.

The autoregressive procedure uses the Cochrane-Orcutt serial autocorrelational error correction method. This method locates the minimum sum of squares of errors if iterated until convergence. For convergence to be achieved, the absolute value of ρ must be less than one. The use of serial autocorrelation correction is required here in order to reduce autocorrelational errors resulting from excluding work load explanatory variables (e.g., travel time) from the regression model.

The general form of this model is:

$$Y_t = \text{constant} + \beta \cdot X_t + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\varepsilon_t = \rho \cdot \varepsilon_{t-1} + v_t$$

where

$$v_t \sim \text{IN}(0, \sigma^2), \varepsilon_t \sim \text{N}(0, \sigma^2), \text{ and } |\rho| < 1$$

- Y_t the dependent time series variable
- x_t regressor variables (including seasonal and cyclical indicator variables)
- β regression coefficient(s)
- v_t random disturbance
- ρ Cochrane-Orcutt autoregression coefficient

Baseline Fit Performance

Two non-seasonal models were developed to measure fit performance improvement achieved by complementing non-seasonal maintenance work load models with seasonal indicator variables. The first model was an OLS multiple regression model using *rt*, *misc*, and *time* as predictor variables. This model didn't reduce its residuals to white noise. It produced statistically significant residuals ACFs at lags 1, 12, and 13; an adjusted R^2 of 0.882; and an SSE of 0.168. The second non-seasonal baseline model used an autoregression procedure with serial autocorrelated error correction and the same work load predictors used in the first model. This model didn't reduce its residuals to white noise either. Their ACF was statistically significant at lag 13. This model had an adjusted R^2 of 0.916, an SSE of 0.122, and a ρ of 0.54.

4.1.a Seasonal/Quarterly and Monthly Indicators Model

The non-seasonal work load model was first developed using *rt*, *misc*, and *time* as predictor variables. Quarterly (seasonal) and monthly indicator variables were then added to the model to exploit the time series seasonal behavior. These variables consisted of 11 monthly variables, one for each month (July being the intercept), and three seasonal variables (summer being the intercept). These indicator variables were created by setting their values to one when they occurred in

the time series and to zero everywhere else. This model did not reduce its residuals to white noise. Its goodness-of-fit (adjusted $R^2 = 0.9295$, $\text{SSE} = 0.106$, residuals variance = 0.00126, and a ρ of 0.52) was inferior to that of all the models described in this paper.

4.1.b Cyclical Model

Cyclical indicator variables were created and added to the non-seasonal OLS autoregression model. These indicator variables exploit cyclical/periodicity trends of the work load time series. A cyclical model uses spectral analysis techniques and decomposes the detrended series into a sum of trigonometric functions (sine and cosine waves) with different amplitudes and frequencies/periods. The seasonal/cyclical component of the work load time series at time t (S_t) can be stated as:

$$S_t = \sum_i \{ \alpha_i \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot i \cdot t / n) + \beta_i \cos(2 \cdot \pi \cdot i \cdot t / n) \}$$

where

- n number of observations in the time series
- n/i the period
- α_i, β_i OLS estimates associated with period n/i [frequency (i/n)]
- t time

The trend (time) component was first removed from the time series to ensure that this cyclical model was not affected by time-related non-cyclical variations in the times series. A partial detrended work load time series periodogram is shown in Table 2. It was created using estimates of the spectral density of the time series produced using finite Fourier transform.

Table 2

Frequency	Period	Periodogram
0.000	.	0.000
0.012	85.00	0.098
0.024	42.50	0.190
0.035	28.33	0.308
0.047	21.25	0.010
0.059	17.00	0.007
0.071	14.17	0.065
0.082	12.14	0.089
0.094	10.63	0.042
0.106	9.44	0.015
0.118	8.50	0.022
0.129	7.73	0.027
0.141	7.08	0.042
0.153	6.54	0.001
0.165	6.07	0.025
0.176	5.67	0.006
0.188	5.31	0.005
0.200	5.00	0.005
0.212	4.72	0.009
0.224	4.47	0.007

The periodogram is a useful tool for uncovering hidden periodicities in the time series. It plots the amplitude ($\alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2$) versus the period (n/i) [and frequency (i/n)] for each harmonic (sine and cosine waves). The seven most dominant (highest amplitude) harmonics (indicated in boldface in Table 2) were selected as indicator variables for this time series. Excluding the fundamental (first) frequency (one long cycle for the entire series), these harmonics are the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 6th, 7th, 8th, and 12th. The indicator variables associated with these harmonics are then SIN1, COS1, SIN2, COS2, SIN3, COS3, SIN6, COS6, SIN7, COS7, SIN8, COS8, and SIN12, COS12, where COS7, for example, equals $\text{COS}(2 \cdot \pi \cdot \text{TIME} \cdot 7/85)$.

The residuals ACF is shown in Figure 3. The model's predictors and coefficients at the 95% confidence level are shown in Table 3. This model's goodness-of-fit statistics include an adjusted R^2 of 0.9665, an SSE of 0.0874, residuals variance of 0.00103, and a ρ of 0.28).

Figure 3

Table 3

Predictor	B	SEB	BETA	T-Ratio	Sig. T
RT	0.001	0.0001	0.257	6.92	0.0000
MISC	0.002	0.0001	0.652	14.00	0.0000
TIME	0.001	0.0002	0.114	2.59	0.0116
SIN1	0.020	0.0086	0.057	2.34	0.0222
COS2	0.025	0.0074	0.069	3.31	0.0014
COS6	0.025	0.0070	0.075	3.63	0.0005
COS7	0.026	0.0070	0.076	3.66	0.0005
COS8	0.017	0.0066	0.052	2.60	0.0114

4.1.c Combined Seasonal and Cyclical Indicators Model

A maintenance work load model that combines the two types of indicators discussed in 4.1.a and 4.1.b (i.e., seasonal and cyclical) was also developed and fitted. The model's

residuals ACF is shown in Figure 4. One of this model's residuals ACF is statistically significant (ACF = - 0.195, Box-Ljung statistic = - 0.188) (more about this in Part 5).

Figure 4

The model's predictors and coefficients at the 95% confidence level are shown in Table 4. Its goodness-of-fit (adjusted $R^2 = 0.9676$, SSE = 0.0854, residuals variance = 0.00101, and a ρ of 0.30) was very good.

Table 4

Predictor	B	SEB	BETA	T-Ratio	Sig. T
RT	0.001	0.0001	0.263	7.26	0.0000
MISC	0.002	0.0001	0.636	13.89	0.0000
TIME	0.001	0.0002	0.111	2.60	0.0112
JAN	0.031	0.0126	0.053	2.49	0.0151
SIN1	0.019	0.0084	0.054	2.29	0.0247
COS2	0.025	0.0073	0.070	3.40	0.0011
COS6	0.025	0.0069	0.072	3.57	0.0006
COS7	0.021	0.0071	0.063	2.98	0.0038
COS8	0.017	0.0065	0.053	2.65	0.0098

4.2 Stochastic Models

4.2.a Seasonal ARIMA Model

Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models (also known as Box-Jenkins models) are stochastic models that fit and forecast a time series using a combination of autoregressive (AR) and/or moving average (MA) processes. Furthermore, first or higher order time series differencing is frequently required before using these stochastic models. Key to developing an accurate ARIMA model is the careful analysis of the behaviors of the time series autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions (ACF and PACF).

Figure 5 shows the ACF of the work load time series. It shows an initially decaying then increasing ACF.

Figure 5

To ensure stationarity (i.e., time series statistical behavior not changing over time), this series was differenced. The ACF and PACF of the differenced time series are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. Both of the differenced ACF and PACF appear to cut off after the first lag. This behavior is not classical of ARIMA time series models. Experience, however, indicates that for such ACF and PACF behaviors, we should attempt to determine which of the ACF or the PACF cuts off more abruptly. If the ACF dies down more abruptly than the PACF, then the model should be tentatively identified as a non-seasonal moving average model of order q . If the PACF dies down more abruptly than the ACF, then the model should be tentatively identified as a non-seasonal autoregressive model of order p . If both the ACF and PACF cut off equally abruptly, then both of the above models should be considered in selecting the best model (Ref. 1).

Figure 6

Figure 7

The ACF and PACF appeared to cut off equally abruptly, suggesting that a first-order autoregressive and moving average ARIMA model should be considered. Since the work load time series has a seasonal component, a simple first-order seasonal autoregressive process was initially considered. This $(1\ 1\ 1)(1\ 0\ 0)_{12}$ model did not reduce its residuals to white noise. The residuals ACF was statistically significant at lag 13. A seasonal autoregressive process at lag 13 (AR13) was then added to the model. The modified model, $(1\ 1\ 1)(1\ 0\ 0)_{12}(P13)$, effectively reduced its residuals to white noise as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8

The model's coefficients, shown in Table 5, satisfied necessary stationarity and invertibility conditions as the absolute value of each AR or MA coefficient was less than one and the sum of all AR coefficients was also less than one. The model's first-order seasonal autoregressive process (SAR1) was not statistically significant. Removing this component from the model, however, produced a model with significantly inferior goodness-of-fit in terms of AIC, SBC, SSE, and residuals variance. The (1 1 1) (1 0 0)₁₂ (P13) model was retained and carried forward to the next phase of the analysis.

Table 5

Predictor	B	SEB	T-Ratio	Sig. T
AR1	0.506	0.1545	3.27	0.0016
AR13	0.244	0.1186	2.05	0.0433
MA1	0.865	0.1007	8.59	0.0000
SAR1	0.163	0.1235	1.32	0.1919
RT	0.001	0.0001	6.24	0.0000
MISC	0.002	0.0001	13.83	0.0000

4.2.b *Seasonal ARIMA With Indicator Variables Model*

Finally, seasonal and cyclical indicator variables developed and used in Parts 4.1.a and 4.1.b were added to the seasonal ARIMA model developed in Part 4.2.a. As shown in Figure 9, this model reduced its residuals ACF to white noise. Its goodness-of-fit (adjusted $R^2 = 0.9675$, $SSE = 0.0826$, residuals variance = 0.00099) was the best of all models developed.

Figure 9

This model's predictors and coefficients are shown in Table 6. This model's coefficients satisfied necessary

stationarity and invertibility conditions as the absolute value of each AR or MA coefficient was less than one and the sum of all AR coefficients was also less than one.

Table 6

Predictor	B	SEB	T-Ratio	Sig. T
AR1	0.287	0.130	2.21	0.0302
AR13	0.231	0.130	1.77	0.0806
MA1	0.967	0.081	11.90	0.0000
SAR1	0.161	0.126	1.27	0.2079
RT	0.001	0.000	6.37	0.0000
MISC	0.002	0.000	14.69	0.0000
SIN1	0.040	0.013	3.15	0.0024
COS2	0.022	0.006	3.45	0.0009
COS3	-0.014	0.006	-2.53	0.0135
COS6	0.024	0.010	2.44	0.0171
COS7	0.023	0.010	2.38	0.0200
Constant	0.001	0.000	2.84	0.0058

5. *EVALUATION OF MODELS*

The goodness-of-fit statistics for each of the models developed in Part 4 are summarized in Table 7. The table also includes the mean absolute percent forecast error for the five withheld observations. Three goodness-of-fit statistics are included in the table. These fit statistics are the Sum of the Squares of Error, Residuals Variance, and Mean Absolute Percent Error in observations 86-90. They were selected on the basis of their application to both causal and stochastic models and relative easy availability.

In causal modeling, the fit and forecasting performance of the seasonal/monthly indicators model were inferior to all other seasonal models. The fact that most of the months were of low or very low statistical significance probably contributed to this model's performance inferiority. The cyclical indicators model fit statistics and forecasting accuracy were very good. The combined cyclical and seasonal indicators model resulted in one statistically significant residuals ACF. However, this occurred at a high order non-seasonal lag (lag 19). Furthermore, the difference between the Box-Ljung white noise test statistic and the residuals ACF at this lag of 0.007 was relatively small. Therefore, this ACF significance was assumed to be due to chance and the residuals were considered white noise. This model's fit statistics and forecasting accuracy were also very good.

In stochastic modeling, the seasonal ARIMA model without seasonal indicators was very effective in reducing its residuals to white noise. However, its data fit statistics were below average. The ARIMA model that used a combination of cyclical indicator variables and maintenance predictor variables provided the best overall goodness-of-fit and forecasting

Table 7

Analysis Part No.	Non-seasonal Model Type	Seasonal Indicators/Predictors	Was Error Reduced to W.N.?	Sum of Squares of Error	Residuals Variance	Mean Absolute Percent Error (in obs. 86-90)
4.1.a	CAUSAL: OLS Regression with Serial Autocorrelated Error Correction	Seasons/Months	No	0.1060	0.00126	11.0 %
4.1.b		Cyclical	Yes	0.0874	0.00103	6.8 %
4.1.c		Combined Seasonal and Cyclical	Yes	0.0854	0.00101	6.4 %
4.2.a	STOCHASTIC: ARIMA	Seasonal ARIMA	Yes	0.1165	0.00140	7.4 %
4.2.b		Seasonal ARIMA with Indicator Variables	Yes	0.0826	0.00099	5.9 %

accuracy. This model was selected as the optimal maintenance work load forecasting model. An overlay of this model's predictions and the actual maintenance work load time series is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10

6. CONCLUSION

Causal and stochastic time series forecasting methods were used to model and forecast maintenance work load. Seasonal work load behavior was modeled using seasonal/quarterly, monthly, and cyclical indicator variables, as well as seasonal ARIMA methods. Both the causal and stochastic methods produced models that provided very good data fit and forecasting accuracy. Cyclical indicator variables were very

effective in exploiting the seasonal and cyclical behavior of the maintenance work load in both causal and stochastic models. A seasonal ARIMA model that used cyclical indicator predictor variables provided the best overall goodness-of-fit and forecasting accuracy. This model was selected as the optimal maintenance work load forecasting model.

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